

Third Focus Group

Research: Taking up your time to say that we'll proceed and provide some context for you. Our study aims to understand your perceptions regarding specific test cases and whether you identify any issues. I'll continue here. So, our presentation is composed of our general objectives, which we aim to achieve, along with some code examples. I'll give you some time to analyze them, and you can agree with your colleague, disagree, or add to what they've said and vice versa. It's really just to spark discussion and understand your thoughts. That's it.

Research: So, the general objective of this research is to understand the relevance of identifying bad practices in JavaScript test code and to grasp developers' perspectives and feedback. What do you think? Does this really impact your work context, or does it not? Just to explain how this will work: for example, here on the right, I have a test block. I believe everyone can see it—if not, I can zoom in to enlarge it—and on the left, there's a brief description, which essentially represents the question.

Research: So, consider that your test case lacks descriptive text, meaning it doesn't have the description here. How does this issue impact the readability and understanding of the test case? I'll ask the question, give you some time, and during that time, you're free to ask me questions or clarify any doubts. Then you're free to discuss—agree with someone else or disagree. Is everything clear? Let me know if you have any issues, as I can't see any signals from you.

P10: Yes, I understand.

Research: Alright, let's get started.

P12: After the question, would we have time to discuss it?

Research: Exactly, you can discuss the question until you reach a conclusion. If no conclusion is reached, we'll move on to the other cases. There are seven cases in total, and that's it. Sound good?

P12: Got it, all good, let's do it.

Research: This case here, folks, is called the *test without description*. It's defined in the literature as a test case that lacks a descriptive text. In JavaScript, when we declare a block of test code, we describe what the test is supposed to do. So, imagine you're in your work environment, refactoring or implementing new tests, and you come across a test case without its descriptive text. How does that impact you? Does it affect readability? Does it hinder your understanding? Or does it not have any impact on you? Now is the time for you to discuss. Why do you think that?

P13: First of all, because people often talk about this, I agree that a test is a form of documentation. So, if you're not describing what's being tested in your test, you're missing one of the test's functionalities, which is to document the application's functionalities—what it should do. So, you lose that, and also, it becomes hard to understand later what the test is doing, right? For me, that's the main issue.

P12: Yeah, I agree too. Because, like, in this scenario, sure, it's just two lines. But imagine a test with a lot of lines. If you come across a test without even a description of what it does, you'd have to stop your workflow to figure out what the test is doing before understanding why it's failing or passing. So, it's exactly what P13 said.

P11: Great! Hey there!

Research: Did someone else just join us? Oh, P11. Let me quickly give you some context since we've already started. P10, did you want to say something? You unmuted your mic.

P10: Could you explain it to him first? I don't want my response to influence his reasoning.

Research: Sure! So, P11, here's how our methodology is working. The objective of this research is to understand your opinions and feedback regarding test cases. How does it work? I'll present seven different test blocks to you, each with a specific characteristic. You'll analyze the code snippet on the right, and I'll ask you a question on the left—possibly probing if you can identify any issues, whether it impacts your workflow, or if you've encountered something similar in your work.

Research: That's pretty much it. I'll give you and the others—P10, P12, P13, and you, P11—time to discuss, agree, or disagree with your peers on what's been proposed. All clear? Any questions?

Research: I believe that's it. You can go ahead, P10.

P10: Alright. I agree with what everyone's said—it affects readability. I think, beyond taking extra time to understand what the code is doing, there's also the risk of misunderstanding what the code is intended to convey. For instance, if we look at this test code here, we have a `getPermission` method that returns a boolean. Now, does that boolean simply indicate permission (as would be natural), or could it mean the opposite? Perhaps `true` is actually saying permission is *not* granted—it could be negating the truth. Something like that. So, you'd have to dig into the method itself to better understand its intent and verify if the rest of the code behaves as expected. I think that's a

key drawback—both in understanding the test code and in the additional time spent trying to grasp the code the test interacts with. That’s it.

P12: I find P10’s point interesting. The lack of a description in the test could cause it to lose meaning over time. Someone might look at the test later, fail to understand what it’s doing, and modify it, ultimately breaking its purpose. Then, when someone tries to maintain that code, it becomes a real hassle. So, yeah, it’s definitely bad for maintainability.

P11: Are you all talking about situations where someone doesn’t use **describe**, like the difficulty in understanding things midway through? For instance, if you execute the tests and someone steps in completely lost, not knowing what’s happening? When you’re dealing with a real project, you’ll have more than 20 tests running simultaneously. That’s exactly what happened to me recently. I was thinking, “Did they show a real project, and is this test above somewhere?” It’s the same feeling I had when I joined this call midway through.

Research: Got it. Anything else, folks? Let me ask another question, just to clarify something personal: Have you ever encountered this—tests without descriptive text—in your work environment?

P12: No.

P13: No.

P11: Yes, I have.

P10: I haven’t, I’ve never come across this situation.

Research: Alright. Let's move on—I think everyone is satisfied with their opinions, so we can proceed.

In the previous case, we talked about a test without a descriptive label. Now, in this *Anonymous Test* case, there *is* a description, but it doesn't clearly explain what is being tested. So, how does

the absence of a clear description impact readability and understanding in tests? In this case, the test has a description, but it doesn't explicitly state what's being tested or what should be verified.

Have you encountered this in your work? How does it impact you when maintaining or implementing new tests?

P10:

This has happened to me—I even laughed when I saw this example. I've run into situations like this before, and whenever I have the permission to modify the code, I fix it to make it as clear as possible.

Like, what exactly should be expected? Is **10** the expected value? What does this **10** even represent? It's confusing for anyone working on the code. So, I always try to make it as descriptive as possible. But yeah, I've definitely encountered this situation.

P11:

I've seen this before too, but in very quick situations. Like, when someone writes a test just to check something temporarily and then removes it. I've seen people do this, but it didn't cause any real problems. However, I don't think it's unlikely for this to become an issue if left unchecked.

P13:

In my case, as I've mentioned before, frontend testing isn't as strict in my work. So, I've studied testing more on my own rather than doing it professionally. I've never seen a case like this either—I've always seen more descriptive tests.

P12:

I've never seen this kind of test either. I think it falls into the same issue as having no description at all. It's almost like the test is missing a description anyway. If you don't understand

what a test is doing, someone might come in later and remove or change it without realizing its purpose. You end up with a test that doesn't actually test anything—it keeps changing over time. So, yeah, maintaining this kind of test is tricky.

Research: Anyone else want to add anything? Do you agree with your colleagues? Disagree? Any additional opinions? Or can we move on?

Alright. Let's go to another case—the third one: the *Transcript Test*.

This case includes one or more types of logging statements, such as `console.log`, `console.warn`, or `console.error`. These are some of the most common logs we see in JavaScript and TypeScript.

So, how do logs like `console.log`, `console.warn`, or `console.info` inside a test case impact readability, clarity, performance, and effectiveness?

In your work, have you encountered tests containing additional logs beyond what the testing framework already provides? Does this impact you in any way? Or does it not matter? Feel free to share your thoughts and experiences.

P12:

I think it adds an extra function call, which does have an impact. You end up testing something that isn't really relevant—you're basically testing the log itself. It introduces another function call during execution, which, even if small, could affect execution time.

I've never seen logs being used in tests. I also learned that logs shouldn't be present in the final product—neither in the frontend nor the backend. You shouldn't leave `console.log` statements in production code. I've never encountered this in a work environment.

P13:

I have the opposite opinion. I worked at a place where logs in the backend were actually required. They helped debug issues in production by showing where something went wrong.

Logs are a tool—if you don't have another way to inspect the code, you use logs to track execution. For example, if an exception occurs in the backend, logs can sometimes make it easier to pinpoint the issue compared to a giant stack trace that doesn't explain anything.

Performance-wise, I don't think logs cause a real impact—they aren't an expensive function. However, I do believe logs can make tests harder to read because they clutter the test output.

So, my view is slightly different, but that's what we're here for—to discuss!

P10: I'm a backend developer, and from what I see, logs are widely used within the backend code itself, in services and repositories, but within test code, they are very rare, you know? So, logs are mostly used in important code. Tests, let's say, don't have a lot of logging. And it affects readability in test code—I'm talking specifically about test code now—because it will have a lot of unnecessary console logs. Since we already have logging in the backend, in services, and repositories, we don't need those console logs in test files.

And this case is quite interesting because I don't know which requirement is affected by this, but let's say it can even make someone a bit lazy when writing test descriptions. Because if you look, the test descriptions here are just "test 1, 2, 3," which means nothing, right? Since the log already provides a better description. So, I'm not sure which requirement this could be related to, but it's something that can happen—people relying too much on what's in the console log and neglecting the test description. Maybe it's related to clarity or something like that.

Regarding performance, I agree with my colleagues—I don't

think having multiple console logs in a test file will affect performance. Usually, test files are executed when deploying the application, and they are not run daily in production. But I do think readability and clarity are affected by this issue I mentioned.

P11: I've had problems with execution order in code before, so I'm not sure if it could influence testing in any way. But whenever I asked ChatGPT to generate some tests for me, it always included console logs and console errors. I don't know if it consumed more resources, but as P13 mentioned, I believe that in companies, it might just be a convention to keep things organized. It makes things clearer, especially for someone new to the project—when they run the tests, they'll immediately see what's happening.

If I'm not mistaken, `console.error` even generates a warning beforehand, just to signal that something is going on.

P12: My only concern is that you're adding behavior that's not part of what you're testing—like `console.log`.

P10: Sorry to interrupt, but logs are much more common in the important parts of the code, you know? Inside a test, it doesn't make much sense to me.

P13: That's exactly what I meant. You're talking about tests. You're testing the log and the function together. In the backend, at least. Logging in tests? I don't agree with that. I think it's actually harmful. Logging in the application helps us monitor things and be more descriptive. I misspoke earlier.

P12: Logging in the backend is fine. There are even logging tools for that. But in the frontend, it's not very common to use `console.log`. You show things to the end user instead.

P11: Yeah, not in the final project. Logging is only useful when you're still developing functions.

Researcher: Alright. All good, guys? Any more opinions? We

can wrap up at the end. Can I continue? Is everyone satisfied? Any other thoughts? Great.

So, in this case, we have a test case that is entirely commented out. You'll see a test block there, and we don't know why the person commented out the code. But it's there.

First question: Have you ever encountered this?

Second question: Does it impact clarity or your understanding of the test's overall context?

Will it affect maintenance? Will it impact anything else that you can identify?

P13: For me, if a test needs to be disabled, you can just use `test.skip`.

A commented-out test might mean that the person was working on a functionality and left it there for convenience.

P11: I've done that before, as shown in the image. Now I'm embarrassed.

P13: Because with tests, you can use `skip`, and they won't run. So commenting out a test doesn't make much sense to me.

P11: I only did it to focus on another part of the code at the time. It was just a way to fix a bug. I used to comment out tests, but I'd still use block comments (`/* */`), which looked a bit better.

P13: Writing code for yourself is fine. But in a team environment where multiple people are developing, it becomes more complicated.

I kept my console clean, but I didn't even realize I was replacing `skip`.

P10: Man, I've done this before, but only while I was still developing the functionality.

While it's still in progress and you're making commits, fine. But when it comes to production, I never did that.

But yeah, usually, tools like SonarQube will flag commented-out code.

These tools help because sometimes you comment something out and completely forget about it.

Researcher: Great. Does anyone else have an opinion? Agree? Disagree? Feel free to speak up.

P11: I agree with my colleagues.

Research: Done. This case here is somewhat similar to the previous one, but what differentiates it? You might not immediately associate what is in this example case, but regardless of the case you encounter, the key question is: Have you ever come across a test block or multiple test blocks that contain numerous comments? In other words, there are a lot of comments inserted. So, has this had any impact? If a test contains too many comments, did it affect clarity or anything else you believe might be relevant? This is what defines this case, known as **over-commenting**.

P12: This actually aligns with a principle we learn from *Clean Code*, which emphasizes making your code as clear as possible. When you add too many comments, it can make the code feel lazy. The impact is mainly the **visual clutter** in the test. By the time you understand what each part is doing, you've already skimmed through several lines of comments, making it harder to grasp the actual test logic.

P11: Over-commenting applies not just to testing but to programming in general. It's kind of ironic because comments are supposed to help, but in this case, they end up doing the

opposite. You can't just go around commenting on every single line. For example, there are two comment lines explaining too much, even mentioning that the ID is `1`. There's a line stating that the ID is `1`, and the comment simply repeats that the ID is `1`. This just **over-pollutes** the readability and understanding of the code.

P13: I agree as well.

P10: I agree with my colleagues. I just think comments are only worth it if it's something very specific. For example, if the `getUserInfo` function returns very specific information about the user, not everything, then that's worth commenting on. If it's something that you can't understand just by looking at it for the first time. But these comments here are pointless. Checking if the ID is `1` doesn't even make sense to comment on. If the email... Of course, the test's objective is already to check what's in `toEqual`. So, I only agree with comments if it's something very specific.

P13: I agree. Only comment if it's a very specific case that can't be explained in the code itself and needs to be commented on.

Research: Anything else?

P11: I think this kind of comment is for people who don't know anything about programming. I think someone who isn't trying to learn and sees code like this might think it's helpful since it describes what each function does. But for someone who already knows how to program, I think it gets in the way. Like, it's only useful if you're studying, not if you're actually working with it.

Research: So, you all understand, right? It's fine, we can proceed. Let's talk about Sensitive Equality. Sensitive Equality

occurs when test methods—like the example here, using `toString`—are used to compare data types and structures in a test. How can this affect the accuracy and clarity of the test results? This is just an example, but if you've encountered similar situations, feel free to describe how it impacts you. In this case, the developer uses the `TrueString` method. In such cases, or something similar, do you find an issue with that, or do you think it's fine?

P12: I think in this case, testing primitive types isn't a good idea. If you have an integer, you could easily compare it with another integer, especially since assignment works by value in these cases. But when you're dealing with objects, where you don't have a value, you have a reference, it's interesting to use `toString` on the object and compare the string content with another object (also as a string), just to see if the objects are really equal. But in this case, I don't think it's a good idea, especially because you're interfering with the test result. In a real-world program, you wouldn't store `13` as a string; it would be stored as an integer. So you're testing something that wouldn't happen in the real world, which feels odd.

P13: I didn't quite understand this **sensitive equality**. Could you explain what that means?

Research: Sure, I can explain. In this specific test case, the developer is using the `ToString` method to complete the test logic and compare primitive types. Let's imagine that in an ideal world, the user's age would be a `number`, either an integer or a float. The developer uses the `ToString` method to conclude the test. If you've seen anything similar, does it impact you in any way? That's the question.

P13: Oh, so it's like switching the primitive type to make a comparison? I get it now.

P12: Right, turning it into a string to compare, whether it's a primitive or a data holder they've created.

P11: I've never seen this, but I'm thinking about a situation where I would need to use it.

P13: Yeah, me neither. I don't think I've ever seen something like this.

P10: I've never encountered this situation either, but I can imagine a scenario where it could be used. For example, in the database, you store a value as an integer, but on the front-end, you need to pass it as a string. Then, you would convert it from integer to string. I think this could be used in that scenario, but I wouldn't consider it a good practice. I'd rather let the front-end handle it however it needs to because it could cause a bug. For example, in JavaScript, there's a number called **NaN**, and it's actually written as **NaN**. But when you convert it to a string, how do I know how it will behave? It might behave one way on a Windows server and another way on a Linux server. So, I think this could lead to a complex bug.

P13: Actually, I remembered a case where you do need this. For example, if you have a mock and a value that needs to enter a form as a string, the form will always convert the value into a string. So, when you get that value and want to compare it to the mock to see if it rendered correctly, you're comparing two completely different types: string and number. I think in that case, it's fine to coerce it to a string to make the comparison.

P10: My suggestion would be to compare both: compare the value, like whether it's successfully converted to **13**, and whether it was converted to either a string or an integer. In addition to comparing the value, compare the type because JavaScript has a lot of quirks with typing, and I wouldn't trust it just like that.

P13: But I think `toBeEqual` will check if it's actually equal, not just a shallow comparison of the two values.

P10: Does it compare both the type and the value?

P13: I think `toBeEqual` should compare both the type and the value, not just equality.

P11: Wouldn't it be better to follow what she said—use two checks? First, check if it's `13`, because it could return either `12` or convert it to a string. Not sure.

P13: No, I mean, you can't compare `13` as a string with `13` as a number. But you can compare the number from the string with the number from...

P10: In a front-end scenario, the front-end needs to receive `13` as a string because if it renders it as a number, it will cause an issue. So, it should validate that the value is really `13` and is a string. If `toBeEqual` works for that, great. Otherwise, it'll need two validations.

P11: I think there are three types of `toBe`. There's `toBeEqual` and others. Those other ones might have double checks. I don't remember.

P13: I don't remember either. I'd need to run a test. But I get what P10 is saying.

Research: Alright, any other thoughts? Do you think it's a problem or not?

P13: I don't think it's a problem if it's needed.

P12: I think it's a problem.

P10: I think it's a problem. None of us are sure it will actually work. Even if it should, it's better not to risk it.

P12: And for cases where you want to compare objects. Objects are by reference in memory. When you want to compare if two objects are equal, testing tools like Vitex already have methods for that. You can use `JSON.stringify()` to compare the values as strings. If something goes wrong with the `stringify`, you'll probably have to debug with Vitex too.

P13: I'm talking about a front-end scenario because, on the front, you'll inspect the element's value, and it'll return as a string. So, you have a mock, which is a number. Then you'll have to compare the number with the string.

P10: My concern is this: imagine if the back-end sends a number, but the front-end expects a string. The front-end will break, you see?

P13: Ah, I get it. But in the case of mocked data, for example, when you're testing an interface... You're getting the data as a mock. You know exactly what's coming to you in the test. So, it's just a behavior test. The data arrives, renders, and shows up in the form. You're in a controlled environment. Nothing will break in this case because your mock is well-defined. So, I think this is fine, especially in the front-end context. It'll have to happen eventually.

Research: Anything else? Should we move on, Alegra? Great, let's move to the last case. Let me add one more certificate. This is the last case. The last one is about **general fixtures**. How does this work? Just to give a bit of context, fixtures are basically mock data. When we mock some data and use it in a test, that's the fixture. In this case, we have a `beforeEach` method. We're mocking the data and using it in the test. One thing you should pay attention to is that these mock data are global. Does that affect the reliability and independence of the test? What do you think of this scenario?

P12: I don't think it's a problem. You have a dedicated hook or function in Vitex that allows you to create a new mock before each test. This prevents you from using the same mock instance

across tests. It avoids interference between tests. So I don't think this affects the test's independence.

P13: My question is whether this is inside a `describe` block or just scattered in the file?

Research: In this context, it would be inside a `describe` block. In the `describe` block, there's the setup, where the mock is created, followed by the test cases. These variables can be global within that block.

P10: I see this test being useful only if you're testing the entity itself. If you're just testing the entity's constructor, like assigning `Alice` to `name` and `30` to a variable, that's fine. But if you're testing something else, like fetching the user from a database, it would be better to mock those database functions. In this case, I think it's safe because you're testing the entity specifically.

P13: Not because of that, but I don't see a risk since you're defining it within a specific block. You're not scattering it around randomly. If the `describe` block is all about that, it's fine. If not, you can always reorganize it.

P10: I agree.

P11: If it's just for testing the constructor, for example, and not scattered around the code, I don't see any problem using `describe`.

P13: But, wait... isn't the `beforeEach` method creating a new instance? So it'll clean up the internal state and create something new. That makes it safe.

Research: Any final thoughts? Shall we wrap this up?